

Research

Evaluate the dyeing performance of silk fabric by using four different reactive dyes

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Abstract : The four different types of reactive dyes Levafix BR blue EFFN, Remazol BR Blue RSPL, Remazol Yellow RR and Remazol Orange RR were applied for the dyeing of silk fabric. The dyeing condition was same for all dyes for producing 0.5%, 1.5% & 3.0% shades. The dyeing performance of dyes were evaluated by using color fastness to wash, color fastness to rubbing, color fastness to perspiration, color strength & Reflectance%. From the above test results, Remazol Yellow RR was excellent compared to other 3 group of dyes. It also showed better exhaustion & Fixation percentage.

Keyword: Reactive dyes, Silk Fabric, dyeing.

1.0 Introduction: Reactive dyes are extensively used for dyeing and printing cellulosic materials and blends containing cellulosic portion. [1] This is the reason behind the fact that researches on synthesis and development of reactive dyes,[2] improvement of their application possibilities and procedures has been practicing mostly by dyers, chemist & engineers.[3] It has also been found

that the dyeing properties of reactive dyes much depend on the structure of reactive dyes. Here the dyeing properties mean the applicability, technology, permanency etc. [2] and structure of reactive dyes is its molecular structure.[4] Method of application and permanency of dyeing is much dependent on the composition of reactive dyes -more directly we can say that on the functional group attached with the reactive dyes. Several reactive dye functional groups have been synthesized, their chemistry has been understood and behavior on application and permanency on the substrate has been discussed in terms of exhaustion and fixation. [5] These two properties in case of reactive dyeing define the suitability, compatibility, permanence, economy etc. of dyeing. [1] [6-8]

The functional or reactive group or groups attached with the reactive dye molecule have direct effect on the exhaustion and fixation of dyes with the cellulosic substances. [5, 9, 10]The other chemicals and dye bath conditions used in the dyeing process also have their effect in exhaustion and fixation, but these are not properties of dyestuffs or only assist to improve exhaustion and fixation.

1.1 Silk: Silk is the royal fibre and its coloration is also an art. There are wide ranges of dyestuff accessible for silk dyeing. [11, 12] Nearly every type of dyestuff used for cotton and/or wool can be used for dyeing silk. [3, 13, 14]In overall the dyestuffs are useful by techniques similar to those of wool or cotton dyeing. Dyeing of silk with acid dyes required more than boiling temperature, resulting fibre damage and more energy. In this study, silk fabric was dyed with four reactive dyes. [14-16]

Figure 1: Structure of Silk Fibre.

2.0 Material & Methodology:

2.1 Materials: Silk fabrics supplied from Sofura silk manufacturing company limited, Bangladesh. The dyes Levafix BR blue EFFN, Remazol BR Blue RSPL, Remazol Yellow RR and Remazol Orange RR was used for the dyeing of fabric purchased from DyStar group, Germany by DBL group, Kashimpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh. The chemicals NaOH, Soda ash, Glauber Salt, Wetting agent, levelling agent were obtained from an Indian supplier (Mark Indian).

2.2 Equipment's: Mini Thermosol Machine was used for the dyeing. The color strength & Reflectance% were recorded on JASCO V-560 UV/VIS Spectrophotometer. Wash fastness was determined using Gyro wash & Incubator. Rubbing fastness was measured by crock rubbing tester.

2.3 Methodology: A continuous dyeing method was used for dyeing silk fabric with reactive dye. Here a common recipe was used by changing the shade percentage of four different dyes. The shade percentage was 0.5%, 1.5% & 3%.

Recipe:

Sample Wt.	5 g	5 g	5 g
M:L	1:7	1:7	1:7
Total Liquor	35 ml	35 ml	35 ml
Levafix BR Blue EFFN /Remazol BR Blue RSPL / Remazol Yellow RR/ Remazol Orange RR	0.5%	1.5%	3.0%
Glauber Salt	70 g/l	70 g/l	70 g/l
Levelling Agent	1 ml	1 ml	1 ml
Soda Ash	10 g/l	10 g/l	10 g/l
Soaping Agent	100 ml	100 ml	100 ml
Time	90 min	90 min	90 min
Temp	60°C	60°C	60°C

Figure 2: Dyeing cycle of Silk fabric with Reactive dye.

3.0 Results & Discussion:

3.1 Dyeing: After dyeing, we got total 12 samples by using four different dyes.

Shade %	Levafix BR Blue EFFN	Remazol BR Blue RSPL	Remazol Yellow RR	Remazol Orange RR
0.5%				
1.5%				
3.0%				

3.2 Color Fastness to wash:

The method of color fastness to wash was ISO 105-C06-C26. The results are shown below:

Dyes Name	Result:
Levafix BR Blue EFFN	

3.3 Color Fastness to rubbing:

The method of color fastness to rubbing was ISO 105-X12. The results are shown below:

Levafix BR Blue EFFN	Remazol BR Blue RSPL
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3.4 Color fastness to perspiration:

The method of color fastness to perspiration was ISO 105-E04. The results are shown below:

Dyes	Perspiration (Alkali)	Test	Perspiration Test (Acid)
Levafix BR Blue EFN	4		4
Remazol BR Blue RSPL	5		5
Remazol Yellow RR	5		5
Remazol Orange RR	4-5		4-5

3.5 Tensile strength test:

The Method of Tensile strength Test was ISO 13934-2. The results are shown below:

Silk Grey Fabric (lbs)		Silk Dyed Fabric (lbs)	
Warp	Weft	Warp	Weft
150	135	130	110

3.6 Color Strength & Reflectance:

The K/S value & Reflectance% was determined by using Data color D650 TM. The results are shown below:

Dyes Name	K/S value	Reflectance%
Levafix BR Blue EFFN	<p>The graph shows the reflectance percentage for Levafix BR Blue EFFN. The x-axis represents wavelength in nm (300-700) and the y-axis represents reflectance percentage (0-50). The curve shows a minimum reflectance of approximately 5% at 620 nm, corresponding to the maximum absorption.</p>	
Remazol BR Blue RSPL	<p>The graph shows the reflectance percentage for Remazol BR Blue RSPL. The x-axis represents wavelength in nm (300-700) and the y-axis represents reflectance percentage (0-40). The curve shows a minimum reflectance of approximately 5% at 600 nm, corresponding to the maximum absorption.</p>	
Remazol Yellow RR	<p>The graph shows the reflectance percentage for Remazol Yellow RR. The x-axis represents wavelength in nm (300-700) and the y-axis represents reflectance percentage (0-100). The curve shows a minimum reflectance of approximately 10% at 450 nm, corresponding to the maximum absorption.</p>	

3.7 Discussion: From the above results of color fastness to wash, rubbing, perspiration, color strength & reflectance%, Remazol Yellow RR is excellent compared to other 3 group of dyes. It also shows better exhaustion & Fixation percentage. Mainly, the dyes contain vinyl sulphone as its reactive group. Vinyl sulphone dyes are moderately reactive, with a dyeing temperature as low as 60°C, and a pH of 11.5. These dyes create an excellent bond/fixation if applied correctly. In these cases, it creates an excellent bond with silk fabric. After dyeing the wastage of dye is least compared to another group. That's why, it can be said that it has more exhaustion and fixation rate compared to other groups. From the k/s value it shows that Remazol Yellow RR dye gives excellent color strength with silk fabric.

4.0 Conclusion: This study was planned to apply reactive dyes on silk fabric rather than Acid dyes. The four different types of dyes was used which contains different reactive group. Here the dyes which have vinyl sulphone group, it creates stronger bond with silk fabric. Thus, based on the results, it can be said that Remazol Yellow RR have good scope for dyeing of silk fabric.

5.0 References:

- [1] H.-m. LU, W. SUN, X.-y. WANG, and J. J. T. A. DING, "Salt-free dyeing with reactive dyes on cotton fabric modified with cationic agent WLS [J]," vol. 5, 2010.
- [2] H.-M. J. T. r. j. Choi, "One-bath dyeing and nonformaldehyde durable press finishing of cotton using dialdehyde and a monochlorotriazinyl reactive dye," vol. 72, no. 6, pp. 469-473, 2002.
- [3] W. Hai-feng, T. Ju, Y. Jing-xin, and Z. J. K. I. Rui-ping, "Study of the dyeing properties of reactive dye with mono-reactive group on silk fabrics [J]," vol. 2, 2006.
- [4] L.-j. LI, Z.-l. HUANG, and Z.-z. J. T. A. XU, "Selection of the auxiliaries for dyeing silk with BF type reactive dyes [J]," vol. 1, 2005.
- [5] J. ZHOU, P. YAO, and L. J. J. o. T. R. XU, "Optimizing cold pad-batch dyeing of silk fabric with reactive dyes [J]," vol. 4, 2011.
- [6] A. J. D. Mousa and pigments, "Synthesis and application of a polyfunctional bis (monochlorotriazine/sulphatoethylsulphone) reactive dye," vol. 75, no. 3, pp. 747-752, 2007.
- [7] W. XIANG, J. ZHOU, Z.-s. J. D. CAI, and Finishing, "Low-salt reactive dyeing of modified silk fabric [J]," vol. 19, 2007.

- [8] H. Xiao, T. Zhao, C.-H. Li, and M.-Y. J. J. o. c. p. Li, "Eco-friendly approaches for dyeing multiple type of fabrics with cationic reactive dyes," vol. 165, pp. 1499-1507, 2017.
- [9] Y. Youssef and A. J. C. t. Mousa, "Structure—reactivity studies of a new polyfunctional disulphide bis (ES-MCT/SES) reactive dye applied to silk," vol. 118, no. 6, pp. 325-329, 2002.
- [10] H. ZHAO, L. WANG, and J. J. J. o. T. R. LIN, "Mechanism of ultrasonic dyeing on cotton fabric with reactive dye," no. 3, p. 16, 2009.
- [11] G. Freddi, R. Mossotti, and R. J. J. o. b. Innocenti, "Degumming of silk fabric with several proteases," vol. 106, no. 1, pp. 101-112, 2003.
- [12] T. Furuzono, K. Ishihara, N. Nakabayashi, and Y. J. B. Tamada, "Chemical modification of silk fibroin with 2-methacryloyloxyethyl phosphorylcholine. II. Graft-polymerization onto fabric through 2-methacryloyloxyethyl isocyanate and interaction between fabric and platelets," vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 327-333, 2000.
- [13] T. Furuzono *et al.*, "Preparation and characterization of apatite deposited on silk fabric using an alternate soaking process," vol. 50, no. 3, pp. 344-352, 2000.
- [14] N. Punrattanasin *et al.*, "Silk fabric dyeing with natural dye from mangrove bark (*Rhizophora apiculata* Blume) extract," vol. 49, pp. 122-129, 2013.
- [15] C. Wang *et al.*, "Carbonized silk fabric for ultrastretchable, highly sensitive, and wearable strain sensors," vol. 28, no. 31, pp. 6640-6648, 2016.
- [16] G. Ricci, A. Patrizi, B. Bendandi, G. Menna, E. Varotti, and M. J. B. J. o. D. Masi, "Clinical effectiveness of a silk fabric in the treatment of atopic dermatitis," vol. 150, no. 1, pp. 127-131, 2004.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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